

Combating Air Pollution through Environmental Management Measures: The Case of Developing Countries

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyze the use of environmental management measures (EMM) in reducing the level of air pollution in the cities of developing countries. Analysis of this study has discovered that although simultaneous application of all three sets of EMM is essential for reducing air pollution, none of the governments has applied it appropriately. The study has highlighted that the best way of controlling pollution is to put restriction on the import of pollution intensive technology, increasing taxes on those, giving subsidies on eco friendly vehicles and fuel, and persuasion of moral suasion; these are considered as the main instruments of environmental management measures. Finally the paper has emphasized a structured framework of EMM which is urgently needed for adopting a comprehensive approach to reduce air pollution and environmental protection and management in the cities of developing countries.

Keywords: Environmental Management Measures, Air Pollution, Institutional Framework, Bangladesh

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INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a matter of grave concern in the present world, particularly in developing countries where increasing economic growth is responsible for environmental degradation. Developing countries are characterized by a rapid increase of energy consumption accompanied by a rapid growth of population and economic activities. Thus the increasing contribution of atmospheric loads of SO₂ and NO_x to global climate change is anticipated and it is really necessary to quantify these emissions in a hurried manner. Thus in order to analyze the trend of air pollution and present role of environmental management measures (EMM) in developing countries various information collected from secondary sources including reports, journals papers, and seminar proceedings have been analyzed and findings have been presented in this paper. Generally air pollution can be defined as any atmospheric condition in which substances (natural or man-made chemical compounds capable of being airborne) are present at concentrations high enough above their normal ambient level to produce a measurable effect on man, animals, vegetation, or materials. In addition, air pollutants are hazardous to human health and can even be fatal at its high concentrations. The most important pollutants found in the air are Carbon monoxide (CO), Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), Nitrogen oxides (NO_x), Ozone (O₃), Hydrocarbons (HC) and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM). In the late 1970s, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) of USA added lead (Pb) to this list. Particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter of less than or equal to 10µm (PM10) is also a major cause of air pollution.

This paper largely based on the review of different articles relevant to EMM analysis in three different cities of three developing countries along with the brief analysis of findings on the state of the air pollution in Dhaka, now widely considered as a megacity. The papers that have been reviewed are: (a) 'Economics policy instruments for controlling vehicular air pollution' by Rita Pandey (1998); (b) 'A CGE framework to evaluate policy options for reducing air pollution emissions in Chile' by Raul O' Ryan, et. al., (2003) and (c) 'Reducing the health care costs of urban air pollution: The South African experience' by Anthony Leiman et. al., (2007). Authors of these papers have focused on air pollution problem in the cities of developing countries and highlighted the way of solving this problem in particular city. Pandey (1998) in her paper pointed out that India still largely depends on Command and Control (CAC) measures of EMM for reducing air pollution. Pandey emphasized that the large scale

effective use of the economic instruments could be more efficient in reducing air pollution. O' Ryan et al., (2003) discussed different sources of air pollution with particular emphasis on the reduction of PM-10 pollutants in Chile and Anthony Leiman (2007), elaborately discussed increasing air pollution accompanying increasing health care cost in South African context. The present study has mainly portrayed the findings of these articles about the benefits of the use of EMM in different cities and most particularly in a problem ridden megacity like Dhaka. Before presenting good lessons learnt from the aforementioned studies, the following section briefly illustrates about the concept of environmental management measures (EMM).

ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT MEASURES (EMM)

Environmental management measures (EMM) are prevalent in most developed countries to reduce pollution. These measures mainly comprise of three basic components, which include regulatory instruments, economic instruments and suasive measures and these components can help to prevent further environmental degradation and to improve the quality of life of the people. Amin, (2007) has illustrated three sets of environmental management measures (EMM):

1. **Economic Instruments (EIs)/ MBIs:** While Subsidy (to give incentive) and taxation/ pollution charges (to create disincentive) are the two fundamental policy instruments, market-based economic instruments include: (i) (Emission) *Charges*; (ii) (Abatement) *Subsidies*; (iii) Deposit-Refund System; (iv) Market Creation-Tradable/Transferable Emission Trade Permits, Market Intervention and, Liability Insurance and Financial Enforcement.
2. **Regulatory Instruments (RIs)/ CAC:** These are comprised of (i) regulatory forms such as laws, licenses, permits, registration, administrative guidelines directives, codes of practices; (ii) Regulatory instruments: Emission of effluent standards, environmental quality standards, product controls, process and equipment standards, planning and building controls, extraction restrictions.
3. **Moral Suasion:** Basic principles of moral suasion measures are: (i) reliance on voluntary compliance by polluters motivated either by the threat of adverse publicity or the prospect of favorable publicity; (ii) Raising awareness through education for environmental protection.

EMM, as enforced in the developed countries, are primarily based on the application of theories associated with (i) externalities, (ii) open-access resources, and (iii) public goods (Amin, 2007). Failure in internalizing externalities, in ensuring property rights, and in managing public goods appropriately gives rise to environmental pollution, destruction of natural resources, and free-riding of environmental resources. Therefore, the developing countries seeking to adopt EMM must first address two major barriers: (i) limited knowledge and application of EMM, and (ii) shortage of professional capabilities and institutional capacities to apply EMM.

REASONS BEHIND AIR POLLUTION

Air pollution is an emerging threat to the cities of developing countries. Growing industries and rapid increase of vehicles are the main agents causing significant increase of air pollution. Reviews from different literatures show that the sources of air pollution may be classified into two categories:

- (i) **Fixed sources** - Energy-generating facilities such as thermal power plants are the main source of industrial air pollution. Factories involved in the manufacture of steel products, chemicals, cement, etc. are another source.
- (ii) **Mobile sources** - Most are private passenger vehicles, taxis or motorcycles. Significant increases in the number of vehicles. Diesel-powered vehicles like buses and taxis, which provide public transportation, cause serious particulate and "black smoke" problems on all the city's major streets.

In Delhi, rapid growth in numbers of vehicles, implying growth in vehicle density causing road congestion, increased fuel consumption and pollutant emissions. According to Pandey (1998), for total emissions in Delhi buses and taxis are the biggest polluters followed by diesel trucks and three wheelers (Pandey, 1998). She mentioned diesel as the main polluter in the city. The key factor responsible for this maximum use of diesel is due to the price difference between petrol and diesel. The demand for diesel vehicles are driven by two factors: (i) diesel engines are less costly to adapt than petrol engines; (ii) diesel engines are more fuel efficient. In case of Chile, major sources of pollution are old buses, steel and petroleum industry. Chile's economic growth has resulted increasing pollution level. Among many factors, increased number of privately owned vehicles have taken toll on people's quality of life. According to Raul O' Ryan, et. al., (2003) as a developing country Chile does not have

the policy and tools to handle this problem. The biggest threat to the health from air pollution comes from fine particles. The studies indicate that fine particles have significant impact on health. For this reason, in Chile several territories have been declared 'saturated areas' for specific pollutants to make people aware of and for policy attention. Other problems related to air are noise in the city, bad smells surrounding fish mill and pulp and paper industries as well as dumping grounds. According to Leiman et. al., (2007) both industry and households are responsible for air pollution in South Africa. However, the 'dirty fuels' are major contributors to urban air pollutions because of increasing number of motorized vehicles in cities. A set of policy and technological interventions needed to reduce such health costs in the high population density areas of South Africa. Although the focus of air quality legislation is on industrial pollutants, the most efficient interventions were found to be at household level. The paper's policy messages are that interventions should begin with households and that further industry controls are not yet justifiable in their present forms as these relate to the health care costs of such interventions.

USE OF EMM TO RESOLVE THE PROBLEM

It is revealed from the present study and different studies have emphasized as well that the use of environmental management measures (EMM) for emission reduction either by emission tax or by pursuing structured policies for technical modifications can solve air pollution problem. Mechanism of environmental management measures (EMM) are; use of Regulatory Instruments (RIs), Economic Instruments (EIs,) or Moral Suasion (MS), which is backed by tax and subsidies, fines, jail and license cancellation or policy for technical modifications and raising awareness for self control. Effective use and actions of EMM depend on following conditions;

- (i) If the vehicle fleet is old and poorly maintained and fuel quality is inferior. These circumstances provide scope for switching to environmentally superior fuel, and retrofitment of vehicles with emission reducing technology, rather than use of fuel tax.
- (ii) Conversely, if the vehicle fleet is relatively modern and fuel is better in quality, fuel taxes are likely to have greater role in effecting vehicular emission reduction.
- (iii) Socio-economic and political scenario of the country.

The analysis of Pandey (1998) discovered that India greatly relies on Command and Control (CAC) measures of EMM for pollution control.

The use of economic instruments has long been endorsed by economists as they are seen to be more cost effective vis-à-vis CAC measures and also have greater chance of successfully internalizing the social costs of pollution to the polluters. But, imposing a tax on this is not feasible since mobile source of emissions is very large in numbers. Therefore, regulator needs to look for alternative instruments/programmes aimed at achieving least cost solution to the externalities. Since vehicular air pollution is a problem and continuous monitoring of individual mobile emission generating vehicle is also not feasible for vast geographical area, the author has suggested some ways to solve the problems. Pandey, (2004) in her another article addressed the fact that tax on diesel vehicles would induce motorists to consider alternative fuels, which is a kind of tool of EMM's economic instrument. Such a tax should be based on the average damage cost caused by the emissions from diesel vehicles. Cars, taxis, three wheelers, and buses running on Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) fuel should be exempted from annual emission tax and be given subsidy sector wise, for example; school and health sector. Emission tax should reflect the difference in damage costs due to emissions from petrol, diesel and CNG powered vehicles. Pandey however, emphasized that tax on emission is more effective than tax on fuel. Because tax on fuel still keeps scope for generating emission if there is chance for economic benefit by using more fuel. So, there should be emission tax based on the externalities it is producing. Green tax¹ as effective instrument is being used in many parts of the developed world for pollution control.

O' Ryan et al., (2003) mentioned in their paper about traditional ways of pollution control for better health in Chile which are firstly, reduction in the production of the most polluting sectors and relocate them-a method being used by most of the developed countries now. Secondly, use of substitution of the more polluting energy producing inputs. Thirdly, use of 'end of pipe' solution like Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP). For reducing critical health impacts of air pollution, emission reduction from vehicle and industry is important as has been addressed by the present study. It will eventually help reducing overall health hazard. Broad category of reducing emissions includes interventions those substitute a cleaner fuel [e.g. Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG) for petrol, Compressed Natural Gas (CNG)], improve an existing fuel (e.g. change the oil distillation process

1. Taxes on emissions or effluents, charge to activities causing environmental damage, charges to products

to reduce sulphur levels in diesel), and improve the efficiency of fuel use. For further reducing health impact of air pollution the methods are: (a) to relocate/phased out the emission sources directly (e.g. relocating a factory to a new site away from urban areas); (b) relocate the emission indirectly; the most obvious example is electrification of high density townships; (c) relocate the 'victim' population or at least ensure that they are fully aware of the consequences of moving into the problem area; and (d) engage in defensive expenditures.

Anthony Leiman (2007) has discussed that increasing air pollution has accompanied increasing health care cost in South Africa and it is related to economic development and environmental degradation. There is state air quality legislation on industrial pollutants, the most efficient interventions were found to be at household level.

PROBLEMS RELATED TO AIR POLLUTION IN MEGACITY DHAKA

Dhaka is one of the mega cities of the world, witnessed a very fast growth of urban population in recent times. The present population of Dhaka is 13.4 million and expected to reach 22 million by 2025 with an annual growth rate of 4.4% (UN-Habitat 2008/2009), compared with an annual average of 1.43% for the overall country (BBS, 2005). The physical growth of the city is phenomenal after independence in 1971 and highest among other cities in Bangladesh due to its geographically central location and socio-economic and political importance (Chowdhury and Faruqui, 1989). Rapid growth of air pollution in megacity Dhaka, Bangladesh has been alarmingly increasing. Literatures and different studies show that air pollution in Dhaka city is reported to be serious and damaging to public health. In the winter of 1996-97, air pollution of Dhaka city became the severest when lead in the air was reported higher than in the atmosphere of any other place of the world (Ahmed, 1997).

Various factors responsible for air pollution in the major cities in Bangladesh, they are; (i) single refinery in country alone can't produce enough lead free gasoline; (ii) serious traffic congestion due to huge non-motorized vehicles in cities; (iii) auto-rickshaw and tempos are the major source of air pollution; although government banned three wheeler in the capital city Dhaka such vehicles still run in other cities of the country; (iv) weak laws and regulations for industrial pollution control. In this regard, a study of impact of auto-exhaust on air quality of Dhaka city has been conducted in the year 2000, and it is revealed that traffic congestion, fuel quality and brick field emission are the main reasons of air pollution in

Dhaka city (Begum, 2004). To control air pollution level at a large scale installation of CNG into the vehicles has been introduced in the country. Air quality of Dhaka city after large scale introduction of CNG vehicles has been improved, where 60% of total vehicles of the country is run by CNG; however the problem still exists in major cities of the country (The Daily Prothom Alo, 2011).

Air pollution can cause drowsiness, eye irritation, throat irritation, persistent cough, asthma, nose blockage, respiratory infections, bronchial infections, colds and headaches in human being. Lead in air can affect the central nervous system, cause renal damage and hypertension. CO in air reduces the ability of blood to carry oxygen and exacerbates heart disorders.

Government policies of elimination of non-motorized vehicle and development of residential areas in the peripheries without adequate commensurate measures are also causing air pollution. Rapid increase of car and very limited use of emission control technology have heightened the problem in Dhaka. However, growing concern over the increasing rate of air pollution in Dhaka city ultimately led to the promulgation of National Ambient Air Quality Standards in Bangladesh in 1997 (Ahmed and Begum, 2010).

ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF AIR POLLUTION AND ITS IMPACTS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

This study has highlighted some economic consequences of air pollution relevant to the developing countries. These are:

- Air pollution is playing an adverse role in increasing public and private health cost expenditures because of increasing health effects.
- Medical practitioners have not been trained properly in relating specific illness or symptoms due to air quality problems (Alam, et. al., 2000). Consequently, it becomes difficult to tackle health effects in developing countries. And it compels to bear huge costs to the public sector and individual of the developing worlds.
- Some cities (e.g., Santiago) require a 50% emission reduction to reach acceptable air quality level (O'Ryan et al., 2003). But a reduction could be very big shock to the economy, author confirms this fear. The impact on GNP will be significant because reducing emissions by 50% shocks the whole economy reducing GNP by 1.5%. On the other hand, stagnation and absence of capital mobility prevent optimal resource allocation among sectors which can lead to dual economy, or increase investment in agricultural sector (Rapanos

V. T. 2007). That would in turn can be treated as a positive impact for creating employment opportunity.

- The development of manufacturing and other industries together with the privately owned vehicles without EMM have injurious effects on water, air, and soil and thus on the peoples quality of life and productivity in the cities of developing countries.
- Reducing PM-10 and fine particulate to reduce air pollution are prime concern of all the countries which have serious impact on human health.
- Due to air pollution many acute and chronic health impacts can be seen, which are: excessive urban particulate matter levels responsible for 300, 000 -700, 000 premature deaths annually and for half of childhood chronic coughing; 400 million people, mainly women and children in poor rural areas, affected by smoky indoor air and effects on productivity, create acid rain on forests and water bodies (WDR, 1992).
- Imposing a tax on mobile source of emissions is not feasible for achieving least cost solution to the externality. Also, continuous monitoring of individual vehicular emissions is not feasible for vast geographical area.

LESSON LEARNT FROM THE ANALYSIS

Some common ideas for solving the problem in the cities of developing countries have been identified in the present study. These are: combination of regulatory instruments (RIs), economic instruments (EIs) and moral suasion (Sis), which can be termed as Environmental Management Measures (EMM). The measure that can be taken through EMM are: (a) reduction of production (travel trips, commodity in industry etc.); (b) use of fewer inputs to produce less pollution; (c) vehicle which are ten years old and above should be phased out; (d) car producers should go for environment friendly vehicle producing with inbuilt emission control equipment and scope for using CNG; (e) banning of two stroke vehicle from country; (f) relocate the high emission releasing industry; (g) awareness campaigns for faster switching to cost effective and less polluting options.

CONCLUSION

Economic growth has resulted in increasing pollution level in developing countries. Among many factors; increasing number of privately owned vehicle is critically worsening people's quality of life. But as a developing country Chile and India does not have enough structured policy framework and tools to handle this problem generating from vehicle and

industry. South Africa is also suffering from air pollution due to their decentralized policy along with industry and large number of vehicle fleets. Imposing tax could not be the only solution, because large number of polluters in the vast geographical area and mobile source makes it difficult to monitor perfectly. On the other hand mass transit can significantly reduce city air pollution. In this context combating air pollution policy option would be best for holistic use of EMM for both transport and industry. However, it is observed from the above mentioned studies that no city management authority has addressed the fact that best pollution control can be made possible through restricting import on pollution intensive technology, commodity and vehicle nor they have good focus on moral suasion. They have mostly focused on economic instruments (EIs) to solve the air pollution problem, albeit Command and Controlled (CAC) and moral suasion approach were found in their analysis as few countries are using. However, moral suasion can significantly reduce the fuel use and reduction of production, thus will reduce the air pollution. In this context the polluter; especially motorists should be encouraged by awareness campaign for example- rapid switch to CNG. It will save millions of life and health cost. Another concern is diesel price which is lower than petrol in many countries which need to be addressed. On the other hand complete structured EMM has not been followed in many countries, and the partial implementation of it has not been even brought under strict enforcement and monitoring. Such condition encourage both transport and industry sector. Government should end price discrimination in favor of diesel against petrol. Also it is noted that the air pollution is not only a problem of urban areas but also significantly increasing to the rural areas. Authority should look in to the rural air pollution problem as well.

At this vantage point it can be claimed that ban of two strokes vehicle from megacity Dhaka alone cannot solve the problem, rather ban of two strokes from the entire country is essential in order to reduce the air pollution. The clean air of Dhaka largely depend on large-scale launching of CNG driven vehicles, introducing lead free petrol and banning 2-strokes 3-wheelers in the outskirts of Dhaka city as well. But, sustainability of this action requires proper implementation under a policy of EMM framework, which means a combination of RIs, EIs and MS. Finally, it is important to remember that simultaneous application of all three sets of EMM is essential for adopting a comprehensive approach to environmental protection and management.

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